

A CROSS-REFERENCE OF MEDICAL TERMS

Jabborova Subhida Abdullayevna

Termiz University of Economics and Service
jabborovasubhida@gmail.com +998912351011
ORCID ID 0009-0003-8445-8405
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11243465>

ARTICLE INFO

Qabul qilindi: 10-May 2024 yil
Ma'qullandi: 15-May 2024 yil
Nashr qilindi: 22-May 2024 yil

KEY WORDS

Adjective makers, word roots, prefixes, suffixes, and the combining form English vowel-O.

ABSTRACT

Medical term or language plays a vital role in a wide variety of disciplines such as medicine, clinical pharmacy, medical engineering, nursing, healthcare management, the academic training, zoological sciences, animal healthcare medicine and public health epidemiology but not limited to those outlined above. While the acquisition of this language is paramount to the study of medicine and related disciplines, it is worthwhile to understand the key underlying principles that constitute the formation of these terms such as prefixes, suffixes, combining form, English vowel-O, adjective makers, and word roots. In this article, the author aims at highlighting and explaining how these principles or rules if properly followed can lead to successful medical language acquisition hereto refers to as medical terminology.

Introduction

Wikipedia defines medical terminology as words or phrases that are frequently used to succinctly describe illnesses, medical conditions, medications, and devices used in medicine. All of these terminologies or phrases take into account medical issues as well as surgeries carried out while a patient is ill. The fields of medicine, pharmacy, and medical engineering can all use this medical jargon. Latin Greek words and "regular morphology" are the sources of most "notable" aspects of medical terminology. I will define a medical term or word precisely as the scientific terminology used to describe the human body, illnesses, and infections that affect it, as well as the medical treatments used to correct and treat these conditions, procedures, and processes that must be followed in the clear, proper language that is understood by everyone in theIn my views, once a substantial amount of medical word roots (for example, renal, gatro,) are acquired, the understanding and usage of medical terms become easier since prefixes, and suffixes remain the same in most cases. Combining words, adjective makers, and the English vowel-O are all essential for the learning and practice of medical terminology. For instance, the medical term to describe the scientific study of the stomach and the intestine would be 'GASTROENTEROLOGY', where **gastrin** refers to the stomach, **enter**-the intestine, **logy**-scientific study and 'O' being the English vowel.In this paper, medical terms that would assist

in the comprehension of disease conditions, procedures, and medical devices use in the medical field are discussed with examples. It would convey system anatomical terminology of the skin, the female reproductive system, the eye, the respiratory system, the ear, the digestive system, the skeletal system, the urinary system, the cardiovascular system, and applications of colors in medicine, diseases and health conditions, and procedures. Diagrams, images, illustrations, and pictures would be used to assist readers to get the vital aspects of the terms related to the anatomy being explained or taught.

COMPONENTS OF MEDICAL TERMS

There are four basic elements that anyone learning or studying medical terms should understand. Namely, **word roots, prefixes, suffixes, and the combining form**. Linguistic morphemes such as prefixes and suffixes have the power or ability to alter the meaning and function of a medical term. It is worthwhile to also look at the origin and meaning of the word etymology. Etymology refers to the learning and study of the “origin of words” or terms. Hence, the medical term or word pathology was formed from path meaning disease and logy referring to scientific study. Therefore, the word pathology was composed from those terms combining with the English vowel ‘O’ to mean the scientific study of disease. From this word pathology, a word root together with the suffix - ologist, a medical term Pathologist for a specialist who study diseases and their conditions is derived. Thrombosis would be a condition of blood clot, and gastritis is an inflammation of the stomach which is also a condition of the stomach. There is a basic difference between the English word roots in a sentence and a medical word root. In medical language, the word root will not fit in a sentence without any modifications such as adding adjective makers, prefixes, or suffixes, otherwise the meaning of the sentence or statements make no sense while this is the opposite with most ‘word roots in modern standard English’ because medical word roots are sourced from many different language aspects. For instance, the medical term for a condition of the heart is “cardiacus”, “from the Greek kardía”. If a Physician says the “patient suffers from kardía event,” to mean bradycardia would not convey any sensible meanings about that statement even to the nurses unless the resultant medical term **Bradycardia** is formed by combining it with adjective maker -ac or prefix **brady**. However, in modern English, it is enough to say the patient suffers from slow heart beat which is the meaning of the medical term bradycardia. Also, the eye, ear, nose, penis, skin, head, stomach, make meaningful sentences without any modification in the English language. They are therefore standalone word roots.

PREFIXES, SUFFIXES, THE COMBINING FORM, AND WORD ROOTS

As pointed out earlier in the introduction portion of this document, a prefix is at the start or beginning of a word or term while a suffix is at the end of the term or word. Both prefix and suffix modify the entire medical term. For example, hydrotherapy means the treatment of diseases or illness with water. The prefix hydro means water, and the word root therapy means treatment. The combining form usually joins two or more-word roots together by adding the English vowel “O” to the word roots to get the entire new medical terms. This according to Wikipedia possess a great challenge to students since word roots are from different sources. The following examples contain prefix, word roots, and suffixes. Transgastric, epigastric, gastritis, gastric, subgastic, pathology, adenoma, cervical, dentist, erythrocytes, histology, renal, thrombosis, tonsillectomy, nephritis, endometritis, anemia, polyarthritis, sublingual, hypoglycaemia, hypertension, thermometer, electrocardiogram, cardiogram, ostemalacia,

leucoderma, chromocytes, polio myelitis, and gastroenterology. Note that if the combining suffix starts with a vowel, then the combining vowel "O" is not used. For example, Adenoma, Chromatura, and cyanosis. Where two or more body parts are used in situation when a patient for example has medical conditions of both the stomach and the intestine, the two body parts would form the medical term gastroenteritis meaning inflammation of the stomach and the intestines. In this example, gastric means the stomach, inter referring to the intestines, and itis means inflammation. They are fused together with the vowel 'O' resulting in the above medical term.

DIRECTIONS AND ANATOMICAL POSITIONS FOR MEDICAL STUDIES

Within the medical domain, it is presumed that the human anatomy is oriented front (Sulaiman, 2009; Dauda, 2013), with the head, eye, toe, heels, and arms grouped together with the palm facing front. Sulaiman's medical dictionary refers to this position as the Anatomical position (2009). The several medical positions, planes, and orientations that are used to identify or characterize different parts of the human body are listed here. There are several positions that can be identified: superior, inferior, proximal, distal, lateral, and medial. Sagittal, transverse, and coronal planes are among the planes studied in medicine, just as they are in mathematics. The human body is divided left and right by the sagittal plane.

BASIC COMMON MEDICAL TERMS OF THE SKIN AND ITS DISEASES

The importance of color in the assessment, and treatment of illness that affect the human body cannot be overemphasized. For example, blue baby means the baby is born with cyanosis. The skin is a sensitive organ which forms a protective barrier against germs, bacteria, fungi, and organisms. It performs dull functions by keeping what is inside of the body inside and keeps what is outside of the body outside. The skin also assists in the regulation and maintenance of constant body temperature, and skin color. It protects us from the sun rays (Clement, 2009) more especially the epidermis and the dermis as well as the fatty layer of the subcutaneous tissues. Some of the medical terms of the skin are skin graft, dermatome, epidermis, dermis, subcutaneous tissues, biopsy, wart, melanocyte, and subcutis are just a few of the medical terms related to the skin. It is useful to briefly explain the common terms used by Dermatologists when patients with skin conditions or performing surgery on the skin to examine the cause of death of an organism including animals.

Conclusion

Assuming a visit to the office of a Dermatologist (a specialist of the disorders conditions of the skin), and the patient chart reads, a biopsy must be performed on the death body to see if the cause of the death is carcinoma. Health professionals around understand what the physician meant, but family members are only familiar with terms for example cancer. This however stresses the need for a campaign about the teaching and learning of basic medical terms among community members. Reviewing the Doctor's report will be that, a small portion of the skin is taken for examination, because he suspects cancer. That is biopsy is the removal of a small portion of the skin for medical examination to know the cause of a disease or illness, while carcinoma refers to a type of skin cancer. It could be malignant, or Students can easily recall the meaning of most medical terms if they study key morphemes attached to word roots to complete the medical terminology. For example, in carcinoma, carcin means cancer, and the suffix - oma gives one the clue of a type of cancer. Other prefixes and suffixes include cutan/e-skin, dermat/o-skin, logist-refers to a person who study or specialist, surg-operate on a person

or animal, gnosis-, secret-to produce, thesis-to organize, vas/o-related to blood, adip-, derm-skin, dermis-skin, mealn-, intradermis, cadaver-refers to corpse, xeno-foreign, graft-transplant, bride-rubbish, abrasions-scraped off skin, plasty-surgical repair, and xenograft- transplant from another species or organism other than human.

References:

1. Anthony R. Kovner and James R. Knickman (2011), Health Care Delivery in the United States. Tenth Edition: Springer Publishing Company.
2. AVERTing HIV and AIDS around the world. Accessed on August 22, 2017. <http://www.averting.org>.
3. Avis, J., Thomas, Lynn, E., Emberly, George Davey Smith, James, D. Neaton and Jeremiah Stamler(2005). Race/Ethnicity, Income, Major Risk factors, and Cardiovascular Disease Mortality. American Journal of Public Health. Vol. 95; Issue 8:1417- 1421.
4. Bitter, J., Elizabeth, V.V., Goozen, H. G., and Pierre, V.A. (2013). Multiplinary Teamwork is an Important Issue to Health Care Professionals. Team performance Management 19(5), 263-278. Accessed on 10/16/2016
5. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. HIV Surveillance Report, 2014; vol.26. <http://www.c.d.c.gov/hiv/library/reports/surveillance/>.Published November 18, 2015. Accessed October 20, 2016.
6. Chaturvedi S.K(2007): Global Impact of HIV/AIDS. The India Scenario. Lecture Notes. www.hiv/aids.edu/powerpoint/slides. Accessed: August 22, 2017.
7. Chen. A, Dietrich. N, Ho. X and Ho. (2011) S: Developmental Neuro-toxicants in E-Waste: An Emerging Health Concern. Environ Health Perspective 119:431-438. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1289/ehp.1002452>. Retrieved from <http://ehp.niehs.nih.gov/1002452/>
8. Clement I. (2009) Basic Concepts of community Health Nursing. 2nd Edition: India, Jaypee Medical publishers.
9. Dauda M. (2013) Community response to HIV/AIDS Management in Mbazwana, Mngqobokazi, and Mseleni communities. Unpublished Master's thesis. Public Health Epidemiology.
10. David, AEP(2009) Essentials of Human Anatomy and Physiology.
11. Davi-Ellen Chambner (2012) Medical Terminology. Short Course. 6th Edition. Elsevter Publishers. USA.
12. Davis Jane Antipuesto (2009). Primary Health Care Definition, Goals, Principles and Strategies. <http://www.nursing crib.com>. Accessed 10/15/2016.
13. Dejo Olowu, 'Menace of E-Wastes in Developing Countries (2012): An Agenda for Legal esponses'8/1Law Environment and Development Journal: Available at <http://www.lead journal.org/content/12059.pdf>
14. Jabborova, S. (2023). TIBBIYOTGA OID TERMINLARNING TARJIMASI VA LUG'ATLARDA BERILISHI. Центральноазиатский журнал образования и инноваций, 2(11 Part 3), 174-177.14.